

Optimum boundaries for maximum load-carrying capacity for misaligned water-lubricated composite journal bearing based on elastohydrodynamic lubrication

Wonvin Kim, Su Hyun Lim, Wonki Kim, Donghyeon Cho, Kiyaranu Putra Pakartiwan, Muhammad Salman Sarfraz, Seong Su Kim*

Department of Mechanical Engineering, KAIST

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01. INTRODUCTION

Composite bearing liner

Corrosion resistance

Design Flexibility^[9]

Fatigue^[10]

Tribological behavior^[7,8]

Strength & Stiffness^[11]

Journal bearing

Geometry

Lubricant

Viscosity, μ ; Density, ρ

Operating condition

Angular velocity, ω ; Load, W

Bearing materials

Elastic constants, C_{ij}

Main principle

Composite Bearing Deformation^[13]

$$\delta = -pt_b \left(\frac{S_{31}(S_{13}S_{22} - S_{23}S_{12})}{S_{22}S_{11} - S_{12}S_{21}} + \frac{S_{32}(S_{13}S_{21} - S_{23}S_{11})}{S_{12}S_{21} - S_{22}S_{11}} - S_{33} \right)$$

Optimum boundaries for maximum load-carrying capacity^[13]

OBJECTIVE

- Provide the optimum boundary for maximum load-carrying capacity in misaligned water-lubricated composite journal bearings
- Analyze the behavior of optimum boundaries incorporating turbulence, bearing deformation, and misalignment

WORK FLOW

Numerical analysis

- Governing equation for steady-state analysis
- Analytical method for bearing deformation
- Boundary conditions
- Algorithm for EHL
- Optimum boundary for maximum load-carrying capacity

Result & Discussion

- Validation
- FEM-based bearing performance
- Effectiveness of analytical approach
- Recommended operating region
- Behavior of optimum boundaries

Conclusion

- Conclusion

02. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Misaligned water-lubricated composite journal bearing

Fluid domain

Assumption:

- Isothermal condition
- Incompressible
- $c \ll R$

Reynolds equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{h^3}{k_x \mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{h^3}{k_z \mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \right) = \frac{U}{2} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial h}{\partial t}$$

where

<u>Laminar</u>	$\begin{cases} k_x = 12 \\ k_z = 12 \end{cases}$	<u>Turbulent</u>	$\begin{cases} k_x = 12 + 0.0136 Re^{0.9} \\ k_z = 12 + 0.0043 Re^{0.96} \end{cases}$
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p : pressure
 c : clearance
 μ : viscosity

h : film thickness eqn.
 U : Linear velocity

Table. Operating condition

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Value
Bearing length	L	m	0.050
Journal radius	R	m	0.025
Radial clearance	c	μm	50
Angular velocity	N	rad/s	100π

Film thickness eqn. w/ misalignment

Projection of axis of journal

Tilting of the journal

$$\tilde{h}(\theta, z) = 1 + \varepsilon_0 \cos(\theta - \phi_0) + \underbrace{\left(\frac{L}{R} \right) \left(\frac{R}{c} \right) \left(\left(\bar{z} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \cdot \varphi_Y \cdot \sin \theta - \left(\bar{z} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \cdot \varphi_X \cdot \cos \theta \right)}_{\text{Misalignment effect}} + \delta$$

Bearing deformation

Load dir. only

Misalignment ratio,

$$\lambda_m = \frac{\varphi_X R}{c}$$

Elastic deformation of the bearing liner

Restriction by housing
Long axial length

■ : Compressible strain
■ : Zero strain

- Hooke's law (Orthotropic material)

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \varepsilon_3 \\ \varepsilon_4 \\ \varepsilon_5 \\ \varepsilon_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ S_{21} & S_{22} & S_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ S_{31} & S_{32} & S_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ -p \\ \sigma_4 \\ \sigma_5 \\ \sigma_6 \end{bmatrix}$$

- Analytical relation of elastic deformation and pressure

$$\begin{aligned} \delta &= -pt_b \left(\frac{S_{31}(S_{13}S_{22} - S_{23}S_{12})}{S_{22}S_{11} - S_{12}S_{21}} + \frac{S_{32}(S_{13}S_{21} - S_{23}S_{11})}{S_{12}S_{21} - S_{22}S_{11}} - S_{33} \right) \\ &= -pt_b \lambda \end{aligned}$$

← Deformation parameter

- Deformation coefficient

$$\begin{aligned} C_d &= \frac{t}{c} \left(\frac{R}{c} \right)^2 \mu N \left(\frac{S_{yx}(S_{xy}S_{zz} - S_{zy}S_{xz})}{S_{xz}S_{zx} - S_{zz}S_{xx}} + \frac{S_{yz}(S_{xy}S_{zx} - S_{zy}S_{xx})}{S_{xz}S_{zx} - S_{zz}S_{xx}} - S_{yy} \right) \\ &= \frac{t}{c} \left(\frac{R}{c} \right)^2 \mu N \lambda \end{aligned}$$

Structural domain

Constitutive equation of the bearing liner

$$\rho \ddot{u}_i = \frac{\partial \sigma_{ji}}{\partial x_j} + f_i \text{ in } D$$

Weak formulation

$$\int \sigma_{ji} \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} d\Omega + \int (\hat{k}_{ij}(u_j - g_j) - t_i) \bar{u}_i d\Gamma = \int f_i * \bar{u}_i d\Omega \text{ in } D$$

where

$$\underline{u}_i = u_x \hat{i} + u_y \hat{j} + u_z \hat{k}$$

Displacement

$$\underline{f}_i = f_x \hat{i} + f_y \hat{j} + f_z \hat{k}$$

Body force

$$\underline{\sigma}_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl}$$

Stress-strain

Discretization

Volume element

Surface element

Global matrix eqns.

$$K_{pq} u_q = L_p$$

K_{pq} : Global stiffness matrix
 L_p : Global load vector

u_q : Displacement vector

Table. Bearing materials

	t_b	E	E_{11}	E_{22}	E_{33}	ν	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}
Unit	(mm)		(GPa)								(GPa)		
Steel	1	200				0.3							
Glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP), PEEK	1		6.2	6.2	2.1		0.408	0.41	0.41		2.11	0.98	0.98
Low-density polyethylene (LDPE)	1	0.09				0.35				0.033			

Fluid domain

Reynolds boundary condition (Cavitation):

$$p = 0 \text{ on } B \quad p = \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = 0 \text{ on } \partial B$$

Axial B.C.

$$p_{z=0} = p_{z=L} = 0$$

Bearing liner

- Free traction, $f_i = 0$ at sides
- Traction force; Pressure fields at inner surface
- Fixed condition, $u_i = 0$ at outer surface

At Outer surface, $u_i = 0$

At Inner surface, $f_i = \sigma_{ji} n_j$ (Hydrodynamic pressure)

At Axial-end surface, $f_i = 0$

Algorithm

Options

- I. Constitutive equation (FEM)
- II. Analytical relation

Bisection method-based algorithm

03. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Validation (Static performance)

Cf. Film thickness eqn.

$$h(\theta, z) = c + e_0 \cos(\theta - \varphi_0) + \tan \gamma \cdot \left(z - \frac{L}{2} \right) \cos(\theta - \alpha - \varphi_0)$$

Pressure fields & Film thickness distribution ($\epsilon_0 = 0.9, \lambda_m = 0.1$)

Steel

GFRP

LDPE

Pressure

Film thickness distr.

Pressure

Film thickness distr.

Laminar

Re 5000

Bearing performances

- Suppression of the wedge effect caused by bearing deformation

FEM vs. Analytical method ($\epsilon_0 = 0.9, \lambda_m = 0.1$)

At maximum pressure;

FEM vs. Analytical method ($\epsilon_0 = 0.9, \lambda_m = 0.1$)

At maximum pressure;

FEM vs. Analytical method ($\epsilon_0 = 0.9, \lambda_m = 0.1$)

At maximum pressure;

Turbulence & Misalignment

Turbulence effect

Cf. Given: Load, Velocity, Viscosity (μ)

Bearing deformation & Misalignment

Bearing deformation effect

Bearing deformation & Misalignment

Separation point: A point where indicated effects become significant

Cf. Given: Load, Velocity, Viscosity (μ)

04. CONCLUSION

1. This study is the first to propose the **optimal boundary for achieving maximum load-carrying capacity, incorporating the effects of turbulence, bearing deformation, and misalignment.**
2. The inclusion of these factors **narrowed the recommended operating range,** highlighting the importance of considering them to ensure the high reliability of the system.
3. Furthermore, this research introduces **novel frameworks** to explain **the shift in optimal boundaries for maximum load-carrying capacity** caused by **turbulence, bearing deformation, and misalignment.**

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**THANK YOU FOR
YOUR ATTENTION!**

Figure 7. Validation of this work with the reference ($R = 30$ mm, $L = 66$ mm, $c = 0.03$ mm, $n = 3000$ r/min, $\epsilon_0 = 0.8$) pressure fields at different angle γ of misalignment (a) $\gamma = 0^\circ$, (b) $\gamma = 0.004^\circ$, (c) $\gamma = 0.007^\circ$, (d) $\gamma = 0.01^\circ$ for $\psi_0 = \alpha = 0^\circ$, (e) $\gamma = 0^\circ$, (f) $\gamma = 0.01^\circ$, (g) $\gamma = 0.02^\circ$, (h) $\gamma = 0.03^\circ$ for $\psi_0 = \alpha = 90^\circ$, (i) load-carrying capacity, (j) moment, (k) minimum film thickness, and (l) attitude different angle γ of misalignment against eccentricity ratio

Figure 15. A comparison of computational costs in a single iteration

Pressure fields ($\varepsilon_0 = 0.8$)

Re 2000

Re 5000

Re 10000

Bearing performances ($\varepsilon_0 = 0.8$)

